

The oncogenic mechanisms of fusion genes in human cancers

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Abstract:

Chromosome mutations and rearrangements are some of the hallmarks of human malignancies. Chromosomal rearrangement is frequent in human cancers. One of the consequences of chromosomal rearrangement is gene fusions in the cancer genome. We have identified a panel of fusion genes in aggressive prostate cancers. In the present study, we found that these fusion genes are present in 7 different types of human malignancies with variable frequencies. Among them, CCNH C5orf30 and TRMT11-GRIK2 gene fusions were found in breast cancer, colon cancer, non small cell lung cancer, esophageal adenocarcinoma, glioblastoma multiforme, ovarian cancer and liver cancer, with frequencies ranging from 12.9% to 85%. In contrast, four other gene fusions (mTOR-TP53BP1, TMEM135-CCDC67, KDM4-AC011523.2 and LRRC59-FLJ60017) are less frequent. Both TRMT11-GRIK2 and CCNH-C5orf30 are also frequently present in lymph node metastatic cancer samples from the breast, colon and ovary. Thus, detecting these fusion transcripts may have significant biological and clinical implications in cancer patient management. One of these fusion genes called MAN2A1-FER generated a constitutively activated tyrosine protein kinase. The fusion translocates FER kinase from the cytoplasm to Golgi apparatus. The fusion protein ectopically phosphorylates the N-terminal domain of EGFR, and activates the EGFR signaling pathway in the absence of a ligand. MAN2A1-FER has been found in a variety of human malignancies. It transforms immortalized cell lines into highly aggressive cancer cells. Expression of MAN2A1-FER produces spontaneous liver cancer in animals. Cancer cells positive for MAN2A1-FER are highly sensitive to several tyrosine kinase inhibitors, and can be targeted by genome therapy intervention. Thus, targeting at MAN2A1-FER or other oncogenic fusion genes may hold promise to treat human cancer effectively.

Keywords:

Fusion gene, recombination, targeting, cancer.

Figure 1: Diagram of Genome therapy against fusion gene breakpoint in human cancer. For detail, see Chen et al, Nature Biotechnology 2017, 33, 543-550.

References:

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Biography :

Dr. Luo has been studying molecular mechanisms of human malignancies in the last 32 years. Currently, he is a Professor of Pathology and Director of High Throughput Genome Center at University of Pittsburgh. In the last 20 years, Dr. Luo has been largely focusing on the genetic and molecular mechanism of human prostate and hepatocellular carcinomas. In this period, his group has identified and characterized several genes that are related to prostate cancer and hepatocellular carcinoma, including SAPC, myopodin, CSR1, GPx3, ITGA7, MCM7, MCM8, MT1h and GPC3. He has characterized several signaling pathways that play critical role in prostate cancer development, including Myopodin-ILK-MCM7 inhibitory signaling, myopodin-zyxin motility inhibition pathway, CSR1-CPSF3, CSR1-SF3A3 and CSR1-XIAP apoptotic pathways, MT1h-EHMT1 epigenomic signaling, ITGA7-HtrA2 tumor suppression pathway, GPx3-PIG3 cell death pathway, AR-MCM7, MCM7-SF3B3 and MCM8-cyclin D1 oncogenic pathways. He proposed prostate cancer field effect in 2002. He is one of the pioneers in utilizing high throughput gene expression and genome analyses to analyze field effects in prostate cancer and liver cancer.

Targeting Transcription Factors by Natural Agents for Cancer Therapy

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Abstract:

Signal Transducers and Activators of Transcription (STATs) comprise an important class of transcription factors that have been implicated in a wide variety of essential cellular functions related to proliferation, survival, and angiogenesis. Among various STAT members, STAT3 is frequently overexpressed in tumor cells as well as tissue samples, and regulates the expression of numerous oncogenic genes controlling the growth and metastasis of tumor cells. I will briefly discuss the importance of STAT3 as a potential target for cancer therapy and also provide novel insights into various classes of existing pharmacological inhibitors of this transcription factor that can be potentially developed as anti-cancer drugs.

Keywords:

Signal Transducers, Activators, Tumor cells.

Biography:

Prof. Gautam Sethi joined Department of Pharmacology, Yong Loo Lin School of Medicine, National University of Singapore in 2008 as an Assistant Professor and was promoted to Associate Professor in 2015. The focus of his research over the past few years has been to elucidate the mechanism (s) of activation of oncogenic transcription factors such as NF-kB/STAT3 by carcinogens and inflammatory agents and the identification of novel inhibitors of these proteins for prevention of and therapy for cancer. The findings of his research work have so far resulted in more than one hundred and fifty scientific publications in high impact factor peer reviewed journals and several international awards. He currently serves as an Academic Editor for PLOS, editorial board member of Scientific Reports, Pharmacological Research, BMC Cancer, Frontiers in Pharmacology, Frontiers in Oncology, and ad-hoc reviewer for several other international journals.

Diet- cancer relationship

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Abstract:

Cancer is one of the leading causes of death worldwide

Lifestyle is largely responsible for the common cancers in Western countries. Dietary fat and chemical toxins have been hypothesized to be the key factors.

The great interest during the last several decades in diet and human cancer derives from the large variations in rates of specific cancers among countries, coupled with the dramatic changes in cancer incidence among populations emigrating to regions with different rates. Such observations indicate the importance of potentially modifiable factors in the cause and prevention of cancer, and a role of diet has been suggested by strong correlations between cancer rates and national per capita intake of specific nutrients.

In this presentation, I will attempt to summarize current information on the relation of diet to the most important human cancers. Emphasis will be given to dietary causes of cancer and how lifestyle changes, such as following a healthy diet, could prevent 30–50% of all cancer. It is well known now that a healthy balanced diet with plenty of fiber, fruit and vegetables and less red and processed meat and salt can help cut cancer risk. Moreover, eating a healthy, balanced diet can help you keep a healthy body weight. Keeping a healthy weight is important, because obesity is the second biggest preventable cause of cancer after smoking.